

SELF-HEALING OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES IN A SPACE ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT: In research funded by the European Space Agency (ESA), the use of functional repair components stored inside hollow reinforcing fibres are being considered as a self-repair system for future composite space structures. The incorporation of a self-repair capability within a composite material has been investigated by a number of workers [1-5]. To extend the existing terrestrial self-healing concept for composite structures operating in space, certain aspects of the environment, the nature of the damage threat, the location and frequency of the hollow filaments, and the choice of repair resin have to be considered before a technical solution can be derived. This paper considers the placement of self-healing plies to match the damage threat, the influence the space environment has upon the healing delivery system and the selection of the healing resin. The experimental investigation of the outgassing performance of the healing system to cope with the challenging high vacuum of space is also discussed.

KEYWORDS: Self-repair, space environment, impact damage

INTRODUCTION

Advanced fibre reinforced composite materials offer considerable scope for stiffness-critical space structures, such as bus and solar array structures, and for dimensionally stable space structures, such as optical benches and antenna systems. In these applications certain physical properties of the composite material have to be optimised, namely modulus, coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), coefficient of moisture expansion (CME), outgassing, specific heat, thermal conductivity, fibre volume, void content and density [6].

The use of functional healing components stored inside composite materials to restore physical properties after damage has been advocated since the 1990's [7]. Incorporation of hollow glass fibres within a structural composite laminate offers the advantage of being able to store additional functional components for composite self-repair systems [8]. To extend the existing terrestrial self-healing concept for composite structures operating in space, certain aspects of the environment, the nature of the damage threat, the location of the hollow filaments, and the choice of repair resin have to be considered before a technical solution can be derived.

THE NEED FOR SELF-REPAIR IN THE SPACE ENVIRONMENT

Terrestrial composite structures can be damaged in many ways, e.g. unexpected mechanical overload, fatigue loading at stress concentrations, heat/chemical attack or impact damage arising from collisions between moving objects. Foreign object impact to single skin laminates can result in a drastic reduction in composite strength, elastic moduli, and structural durability and damage tolerance characteristics.

Composite structures operating in the space environment are vulnerable to impact damage resulting from collisions with micrometeoroids and orbital debris. The relative velocity of man-made debris ranges from zero, for objects in the same orbit, to approximately 11 km/s for objects in retrograde orbits [9]. In comparison, collisions with meteoroid particles take place with an average velocity of 19km/s [10]. The damage to the brittle composite structures consists of penetration holes with adjacent surface damage and some internal ply delamination [6]. The internal damage may be anisotropic, following the structure of the fibres. For complete penetrations the rear surface damage area (surface spallation) is frequently larger than the entry hole (ratios of 5:1 for spallation damage-to-hole size are often observed for carbon/epoxy laminates).

Space composite laminates can also suffer from internal matrix microcracking. This type of damage can occur within the lifetime of the composite structure due to its exposure to the repeated thermal cycling within the space environment. The magnitude of the microcracks will be dependent upon certain laminate and environmental properties (i.e. mission orbit, thermal properties, fibre and resin properties, number of cycles, stacking sequence, temperature differential, bond strength, stress/strain at micro/macro levels and matrix morphology). Any form of self-healing system contained within a space composite laminate must be able to repair damage resulting from collisions with micrometeoroids and orbital debris or damage arising from thermal cycling.

SELF-HEALING REPAIR OF SPACE COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

In the self-healing approach adopted by Bristol University, hollow glass fibres are used in preference to embedded microcapsules (see for example [3, 4, 7, 11]) because they offer the advantage of being able to store additional functional components for composite self-repair systems as well as acting as reinforcement. This approach has been investigated by a number of workers [5, 8, 12, 13]. A typical hollow fibre self-healing approach used within composite laminates could take the form of fibres containing a one-part resin system, a two-part resin and hardener system or a resin system with a catalyst or hardener contained within the matrix material. A schematic illustration of these approaches is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: A schematic illustration of different hollow fibre self-healing approaches [5]

The exact nature of the self-healing method will depend upon (1) the nature and location of the damage, (2) the potential self-healing repair resins, and (3) the influence of the operational environment. The self-healing fibres could be introduced within the composite laminate as additional plies at each interface, at critical interfaces or as individual filaments spaced at predetermined distances within each ply. In this research project, the self-healing filaments were introduced as a ply located at critical interfaces, i.e. where the damage was observed to manifest itself most distinctly.

DAMAGE AND ITS INFLUENCE UPON SELF-HEALING APPROACHES.

A 16 ply composite laminate with a $[0^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_{2s}$ stacking sequence manufactured from pre-impregnated E-glass and 913 epoxy (Hexcel Composites Limited, UK) was selected for the evaluation of the hollow fibre self-healing approach. Panels of 200mm by 200mm by 2.5 mm were prepared according to the pre-preg manufacture's instructions. This panel was then sectioned into coupons 20mm by 50mm by 2.5 mm for testing. A series of pseudo-impacts were undertaken on the coupons using a static 3-point bend test to determine the nature and magnitude of the damage. The selection of E-glass/epoxy in preference to a CFRP permitted the visual inspection of the damage site.

Different load levels were used to introduce an indentation, representative of impact damage, into the composite laminate. After the initial study it was found that a load level of 1400N was sufficient to generate a range of damage modes through the thickness of the composite without penetrating the laminate. A cross section of the damaged laminate (when viewed parallel and normal to the 0° fibre orientation) is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Damage formation in $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2s}$ laminate manufacture from pre-impregnated E-glass and epoxy 913 subjected to a 1400N three-point bend test.

The damage formation apparent in Fig. 2 now gives some insight into the identification of the critical failure interfaces within this particular laminate stacking sequence, and therefore

locations where the self-healing filaments should be placed. When viewed along the 0° fibre direction the critical failure interfaces are [+45°/90°] above the mid-plane and in the [-45°/90°] below the mid-plane of the specimen. When the damage is viewed along the 90° fibre direction the critical failure interfaces are not as clearly defined. The damage is more widespread with each ply interface having some level of damage throughout the thickness of the laminate suggesting that self-healing fibres should be positioned at all ply interfaces. In reality the damage will be interconnected and therefore one self-healing layer, with sufficient volume of healing resin, will be able to heal damage occurring over a number of different plies. This assumption must be confirmed before the final location of the self-healing plies can be precisely determined. However, in this study, the critical interfaces of [+45°/90°] above the mid-plane and the [-45°/90°] below the mid-plane of the specimen were used for the location of the self-healing plies.

CANDIDATE SELF-HEALING REPAIR RESINS

The selection of the repair resin system will have to consider the space structure requirements, i.e. the type of loading, the operating temperature range, and operating life of the spacecraft. In addition to these requirements any resin selection will need adequate mechanical performance, longevity, compatibility within the hollow filaments, and the ability to be drawn along the damage interface. These critical factors are considered below:

- 1 Efficiency of materials for self-healing application in the space environment
 - Modulus, strength, adequate strain to failure, thermal fatigue resistance, fracture energy, compatibility with fibres, bond strength to fibres
- 2 Long-term efficiency of self-healing concept
 - Degradation versus storage/mission duration, environmental resistance, storage life/conditions
- 3 Stability of self-healing components in the space environment
 - Volatiles content, coefficient of thermal expansion, outgassing/desorption
- 4 Applicability of concept to commonly used space materials
 - Compatibility with chosen process, cost
- 5 Processing requirements
 - Viscosity, shelf-life, one-part or two-part resin systems, activation method, cure temperature/time

Whilst some of the answers to these different factors will be known for a cured composite laminate or a cured polymer resin, there is little information about the performance of a liquid resin operating within a space environment. This limited information forces the screening process to be initially undertaken through comparison of cured resin data. Potential candidate systems will then have to be re-evaluated in a simulated space environment before a clear recommendation can be made. It is highly likely that any optimised resin system will have to be engineered to specifically meet these criteria due to the demanding nature of the environment.

In this research programme a number of different resin systems and activation methods were considered but the resin selection process concluded that a two-part epoxy resin and hardener with a long shelf life, a viscosity of <250cP and a curing temperature <100°C would be most suitable. A number of commercially available candidates fulfilled these criteria but Cycom 823 two-part epoxy resin system from Cytec Engineered Materials was finally chosen for further study.

SELF-HEALING TRIALS WITH PREFERRED RESIN SYSTEM

As an initial proof of concept, a 16 ply $[0^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_{2s}$ composite laminate manufactured from pre-impregnated E-glass and 913 epoxy with single plies of self-healing fibres (placed in the 90° fibre direction) located at the key damage interfaces, i.e. the $+45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface above the mid-plane and in the $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ below the mid-plane of the specimen. The hollow fibres were infused with a pre-mixed Cycom 823 resin system (from Cytec Engineered Materials) containing a UV dye penetrant (Ardrox 985 from Chemetall PLC.) to assist in observing the healing process of the damage site. The sample was then damaged using a three-point bend test (loaded to 1400N see section 4 above). The sample was then heated to 90°C and held at this temperature for 1 hour. During this period time-lapse photography was used to record the migration of the healing resin through the damaged site. This is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Cycom 823 epoxy resin with UV dye infused at 90°C

The healed sample was then sectioned to determine whether the healing resin had remained in close proximity to its original location or whether it had migrated away from its initial interface and along the damage length. A cross section of the healed damage (indicated in Fig 3.) illuminated under UV light is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig.4: Impact damaged cross-section of $[0^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_{2s}$ composite laminate containing healing filaments at the $+45^\circ/90^\circ$ and $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces containing Cycom 823 and UV dye

Fig. 4 clearly illustrates the extent of the infiltration by the healing resin into the damage zone when viewed along the 0° fibre direction. This result compares favourably with the damage observed in Fig. 2 and would suggest that the four self-healing locations are ideally placed within the complex damage network to fully infuse the damage site. To understand the mechanism involved in the self-healing of the damage zone further microscopic examinations were undertaken. This examination indicated the occurrence of crushed hollow fibres under the impact zone (see Fig. 5(a) and 5(c)) and healing resin bridging the fracture surfaces (see Fig 5(b) and 5(d)).

Fig. 5: (a) Crushed-healing fibres located under the impact site viewed under normal lighting; (b) Healing resin bridging cracked interface viewed under normal lighting; (c) Crushed-healing fibres located under the impact site viewed under UV lighting; (d) Healing resin bridging cracked interface viewed under UV lighting.

The result in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 has illustrated the success of the Cycom 823 epoxy resin system in infusing the impact damage site from four key locations. Due to the successful infusion trial, this system was selected for further evaluation under a pseudo-space environment.

VERIFICATION OF THE SELF-HEALING APPROACH

The space environment significantly influences the selection and performance of the different candidate resin systems. In the high vacuum of space, composite materials desorb moisture, which can lead to large dimensional changes in the structure. The effect of moisture on composite laminates has been well documented in the open literature [14]. Previous work has noted that the dimensional changes caused by moisture desorption of cured composite laminate is strongly influenced by the laminate design and matrix material. Another effect the high vacuum environment of space may have on the polymeric materials is mass loss due to

outgassing. This mass loss can for instance be the result of outgassing of low molecular weight components of a polymer. It is obvious that outgassing be minimal because it may lead to contamination of spacecraft components which are mission critical (e.g. optics). A liquid resin system exposed to high vacuum is likely to have a high outgassing rate. In the case of the self-healing approach, the only time the liquid resin and hardener will come into contact with the high vacuum is when the structure has been damaged. However, when the resin comes into contact with the hardener the curing process will be initiated and therefore the rate of outgassing should decrease as the liquid transforms to a solid. To evaluate what takes place under these circumstances an outgassing experiment investigating the resin, hardener and the mixed resin and hardener was devised.

OUTGASSING TEST EVALUATION

The standard screening test method employed by ESA to determine the outgassing performance of candidate space materials is given in document ECSS-Q-70-02A [15]. This document describes a thermal vacuum test to determine the outgassing properties of materials proposed for use in the fabrication of spacecraft and associated equipment. The test defines the outgassing properties of materials at 125°C under 10^{-3} Pa for 24 hours. This is determined by measuring the sample before and after the test to ascertain the recovered mass loss (RML) (i.e. total mass loss of the specimen without the absorbed water), and the collected volatile condensable material (CVCMM) collected on a condenser plate in close proximity to the sample. The collector plate was kept at a constant 25°C during the experiment.

The outgassing test method (as specified in ECSS-Q-70-02A) tends to be conducted on solid materials with very low outgassing rates. However, since a two-part liquid system (with potentially high outgassing rate) was going to be assessed it was decided to undertake some measures to avoid excessive contamination of the highly sensitive test equipment. A sample of material was placed in a bespoke, single Knudsen cell, which was placed in a small vacuum system equipped with a cold trap and evacuated by a turbo-molecular pump. In addition to capturing the mass loss, a mass spectrometer was used to investigate the nature of the outgassing products as the temperature of the Knudsen cell was slowly increased to 125°C. The experimental arrangement is indicated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Outgassing test set-up: (a) Al-foil crucible containing the mixed resin system; (b) Knudsen cell with heater and thermocouples housing the Al-foil crucible; (c) Vacuum chamber housing Knudsen cell connected to mass spectrometer.

Prior to the commencement of the outgassing experiment the Cycom 823 liquid resin and hardener were mixed at the recommended 4:1 ratio. At room temperature the mixed sample has a viscosity of 250cP and will not reach full cure for 6 days. A measured amount of mixed resin is then poured into a small Aluminium-foil crucible (see Fig. 6a). The crucible is then placed in a small Knudsen cell, provided with a heater and two thermocouples (see Fig. 6b).

The Knudsen cell is contained within a small, vacuum chamber, which was evacuated by a two-stage, rotary vane, mechanical pump. This provided a typical pressure throughout the test of between 2×10^{-2} and 6×10^{-3} millibar. From the low-vacuum stream, a sample of the gas was removed via a needle valve into a high-vacuum system, pumped by a turbo-molecular pump. The high-vacuum system operated at typically not more than 2×10^{-5} throughout the testing. This system was equipped with a high-vacuum gauge and a mass spectrometer which was used to monitor the volatile components from the samples throughout the test. Four tests were undertaken to understand how the liquid resin and hardener were affected by temperature and vacuum. The first two tests considered the liquid resin and hardener whilst the third and fourth tests considered two different heating rates (at $3.33^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $1.67^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) for a 4:1 resin-to-hardener mix ratio. The test results have been summarised below.

Test 1: Cycom 823 hardener

- Temperature profile RT to 140°C in 90 minutes
- Increasing number and diversity of components with increasing temperature
- After several hours at 140°C , the peaks indicating the presence of organic components began to decrease and after approximately six hours had more or less ceased to exist.
- When the apparatus cooled down and the cell was removed it was found that the entire contents of the crucible had evaporated.

Test 2: Cycom 823 resin

- Temperature profile RT to 140°C in 90 minutes
- The crucible and cell were found to be completely devoid of any resin, the sample had deposited itself all over the rest of the system, up to and including the cold trap. Thus this material is also very volatile but condenses at a higher temperature than the hardener

Test 3 – Cycom 823 resin / hardener 4:1 mix

- Temperature profile RT to 125°C in 30 minutes
- Organic components were registered by the mass spectrometer from 60°C
- The same organic components were observed as had been seen in Tests 1 and 2, although the magnitude of these peaks began to diminish within an hour.
- Solid sample remained in cell at end of test

Test 3 – Cycom 823 resin / hardener 4:1 mix

- Temperature profile RT to 125°C in 60 minutes
- Organic components were registered by the mass spectrometer from 60°C
- The same organic components were observed as had been seen in Tests 1 and 2, although the magnitude of these peaks began to diminish within an hour.
- Organic components generated at around 60°C in test 3 were now not observed until around 90°C in test 4
- Solid sample remained in cell at end of test

In addition to the experiments to determine the outgassing behaviour of a two-part epoxy RML measurements were taken according to the test guidelines in ECSS-Q-70-02A. In this

standard, the general acceptance limits for outgassing materials (not manufactured for optical devices, or in their vicinity) for RML is < 1% and for CVCM is < 0.1%. The mass loss measurements for the Cycom 823 system are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Mass loss measurements for Cycom 2-part epoxy liquid resin ramped to 125 °C within 60 minutes and held for 24 hours

Outgassing property description		Mg
Total specimen mass before test	W _o	473.98
Total specimen mass after test	W _f	409.57
Mass of material before test	W _m	448.10
Final mass of collector plates after test	W _g	61.24
Initial mass of collector plates before test	W _p	60.53

$$TML \% = \frac{W_o - W_f}{W_m} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$CVCM \% = \frac{W_g - W_p}{W_m} \quad (2)$$

The TML of the liquid specimen over 24 hours was 14.4% as calculated by Equation (1). The CVCM of the two-part epoxy system over 24 hours was 0.16% as calculated by Equation (2).

As expected, the outgassing performance of the liquid epoxy resin system falls outside the existing ESA guidelines, i.e. guidelines generated for cured materials and not for liquids. In the context of producing a self-healing material, the Cycom 823 two-part resin system was selected because it has a very low viscosity and resin gelation occurs within 15 minutes at 90°C. For a standard commercially available epoxy resin this system provides the best healing attributes within the operating environment.

A further point that should be considered is the temperature at which the outgassing products are generated. In the outgassing tests the specimen is ramped to 125°C with the specimen starting to outgas at 60°C during the fast ramp rate (i.e. approximately 3°C per minute) and at 90°C during the slow ramp rate (i.e. approximately 1.5°C per minute). Also, the extent of outgassing above 100°C is a critical parameter because the original ESA requirements were for a self-healing capability from -100°C to +100°C. If, as the outgassing tests suggest, the rate of cure can happen fast enough then the rate of outgassing may fall beneath, or at least closer to, the existing ESA standard requirements. This possibility will have to be investigated further.

Finally, it should be noted that the problem of outgassing would only occur if the surface of the composite laminate has been penetrated. If, the damage were formed internally with no laminate penetration then the self-healing process would pass the existing ESA outgassing guidelines.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work has shown how a hollow-fibre self-healing approach can be used for the repair of space composite structures. The placement of self-healing plies to match the damage threat and the selection of a healing resin has been undertaken. It has been shown that a standard

commercial available two-part epoxy resin system (Cycom 823) can be used for the repair of internal matrix cracking and delaminations. As to be expected the resin system falls outside the existing outgassing performance criteria when tested to 125°C. However, if the composite structure is required to operate between -100°C and +100°C, the rate of resin cure at 100°C maybe sufficient to significantly reduce the mass loss reported within this work. Finally, the problem of outgassing products is only a concern when the composite laminate has been penetrated.

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